

DETERMINING OF PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT SYSTEM AND MANAGERIAL PERFORMANCE IN GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS: EVIDENCE FROM LAMPUNG PROVINCES, INDONESIA

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Abstract

Considering the need to improve the service quality of local government organizations, this study aims to investigate the impact of performance measurement system on managerial performance through organizational learning. The research method used a survey, 144 usable data analysed by using AMOS software. The results of the study show that the performance measurement system has an effect on organizational learning, and subsequently improves managerial performance. However, the performance measurement system cannot directly influence managerial performance. The first implication of this study is providing the evidence that performance measurement systems improve the managerial performance through organizational learning. Second, it introduces to the literature of performance measurement systems in government organizational. Originality of the study extends new insights implementation of performance measurement system in improving managerial performance at government organizational.

Keywords: Performance Measurement System; Organizational Learning; Managerial Performance; Structural Equation Model.

1. INTRODUCTION

The capacity of management and workforce to provide higher levels of performance is critical to organizational success (Qalati et al. 2022); (Do et al. 2022); and (Saadat and Saadat 2016). Performance is always important for profit-oriented and non-profit organizations, because it represents the real achievement of the organization's target and objectives (Tjahjadi et al. 2019). A management control system that can encourage employee operational activities in achieving organizational goals is needed in efforts to increase performance.

The relationship between management control systems and performance has attracted more attention in the literature, Beuren et al. (2021); and Bellora-Bienengraber et al. (2022) have noted the importance of management control systems for organization. The management control system can create company control, assess performance, generate a sense of compliance with applicable operational rules, and protect all assets in the company.

Management control research, the focus on performance measurement systems is used to link strategy with action. Performance measurement systems can change strategy into financial and non-financial metrics that make it easier for management to maintain alignment between

organizational goals and operational activities Louhichi and Boujelbene (2016). The existence of this system is expected to provide an overview to management about business situations and plans. Neely et al. (2005) said that performance measurement systems contribute to the realization of a company's strategic vision apart from making positive improvements in organizational culture, processes and procedures Cadez and Guilding (2008); Chenhall et al. (2011); and Yuliansyah et al. (2019).

The management of government organizations is different from the business, because the goods offered are not actual and involve a psychological influence such as direct service quality to service value of public. This makes public sector organizations more difficult than manufacturing businesses.

Along with the demand for increased public sector services in Indonesia, local government total quality management is very important, and service quality control must be continuously measured. The implementation of performance measurement systems in government organizations often experiences difficulties because in reality many government agencies lack or even do not have information about employee performance in their organizations (Umashev and Willett 2008).

According to Dollyno (2008) limited information can cause performance measurements that are carried out to tend to use up the leadership's time and effort while the results are more subjective. Kihn (2010) discusses the importance of empirical investigations in the service sector to make an academic contribution to the management accounting literature, which has so far focused more on manufacturing businesses. However, number of research in management accounting, is still low especially in public sector organizations, so it is important for researchers to use empirical testing to fill this gap.

Performance measurement systems have been the subject of extensive empirical investigation. Research on the impact of performance measurement systems on performance, however, has yielded mixed results. These few ideas inspired me to undertake additional research on conceptual and empirical conflicts in various private and public sectors of the economy. As a result, the following discussion clarifies much of the concern surrounding the analysis of performance measurement systems, performance, and other determinants.

Literature studies, including by Baird (2017); Baird et al. (2021); and Aljuhmani et al. (2022), have found a strong correlation between organizational performance and performance measurement systems. Organizations that implement performance measurement are better than those that do not (Davis and Albright 2004); (Spencer et al. 2009). However, according to Chenhall (2005) study, there is evidence to suggest that strategic performance measurement systems are related to medium to long-term performance, depending on the type of organizational performance being taken into account.

Balanced scorecard, economic value, and business model, on the other hand, found by Ittner et al. (2003) associated with increased system satisfaction measures but not with economic performance. Similar to this, a study by Lau and Sholihin (2005) supports the notion that organizations with clear performance measures whether they are financial or non-financial

measures have higher levels of procedural fairness and employee satisfaction.

Furthermore, Sholihin et al. (2010) came to the conclusion that manager performance is not significantly affected by reliability on multiple performance measures. However, the specificity of the objectives and the difficulty of the targets as moderating elements determine the impact of this performance evaluation. This review indicates that additional research is needed, especially on the causes and effects of interest when analyzing strategic and performance measurement systems.

Performance measurement systems significantly affect organizational capacity, especially for learning organizations, according to studies by Henri (2006) and Mahama (2006) utilizing a resource-based perspective. In addition, a study by Hall (2011) found that individual learning mediates the relationship between performance measurement systems and managers' performance. Individual learning, on the other hand, differs from organizational learning, which covers a wider range of aspects.

According to Henri (2006), organizational learning involves institutional mechanisms (such as policies, strategies, and models) in addition to new perspectives or changed behavior based on knowledge and experience, all of which are considered as catalysts for improved performance and competitiveness. . There is a research gap because organizational learning as a performance mediator has not been found in the literature (Appuhami 2019).

According to Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle (2011), organizational learning is a process by which company managers gain new knowledge and insights from experiences with people in the organization. This process has the power to change behavior and improve company capabilities. According to Chenhall (2005), organizational learning can change the perspective of organizational members and the way they act in response to change. Therefore, organizational learning can improve performance and even benefit the organization.

Managers cannot manage an organization if they cannot measure it, according to Eddine Bedoui (2012). Effective performance measurement is critical to the successful implementation of strategy and achievement of organizational goals because managers cannot judge strategy effectiveness without evaluation. To evaluate the relationship between strategic performance measures and managers' performance, this study focuses on local government organizations.

Performance reviews, which are often used by local government as opposed to private business, usually consist of a number of components that focus on individual work and workplace behavior. Leaders compare actual work with targets in terms of quantity, quality, and efficiency in implementing performance measurement efforts for individual work targets. While the work is assessed through observation of behavior in accordance with predetermined criteria. Honesty, dedication, self-control, cooperation, innovation and leadership are all demonstrated by employees in their behavior.

Performance measurement instruments offered by local governments are considered as a recent development in public sector organizations. The majority of management of public sector organizations also adopt training and experience in the business sector. In order to meet the

mastery and internalization requirements set by the local government, employees must periodically make changes to training.

According to Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle (2011), organizational learning is an important component for improving performance because it provides business opportunities to change their behavior and improve their capabilities through the acquisition of new information and understanding through interactions with employees.

Thus, the existence of a management control system is an interesting study in the banking industry, especially in relation to strategic performance measurement. Therefore, to close the existing research gap, a study was conducted on determining the performance measurement system for manager performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The contingency approach is used in this study as a broad theory to explain how management control systems are developed and used to improve manager performance, particularly with regard to performance measurement. Despite the fact, Chakravarty et al. (2013) that finding a contingency approach is limited by the difficulty in defining, measuring, and testing complete contingencies without eliminating variable bias among potential contingencies.

Previous studies have used the contingency approach to identify the relationship between various variables, including knowledge management strategy and managerial performance (Kim et al. 2014), management control systems in relation to stakeholders (Serna et al. 2022), and multidimensional performance. performance measures and factors (Ahmad et al. 2022).

The contingency approach is predicated on the idea that good administrative practices, such as performance assessment systems to the contingent variables in which the organization operates, lead to organizational effectiveness. According to Smith, et al (2019), there are specific circumstances or variables that influence the relationship between organizational traits like performance measurement systems and organizational performance. A strategic performance measurement system, according to Rey-Marston and Neely (2010) is a managerial tool that enables businesses to carry out their strategies, monitor performance, encourage local action alignment, offer organizational feedback, and serve as a learning tool.

The complexity of management behavior and management control procedures, such as performance assessment systems, are important aspects of organizational control, according to contingency theory (Chenhall 2003); dan (Cheng and Fisk 2022). Yuliansyah and Jermias (2018) study revealed that strategic performance assessment systems have an impact on organizational learning, which in turn has an impact on performance.

Organizational learning is defined by Antunes and Pinheiro (2020); and Akgün et al. (2023) as a type of organizational culture that is built on consideration for change, adaptation, and acceptance of new ideas in order to achieve organizational goals and performance benchmarks.

Numerous studies, including Escandon-Barbosa and Salas-Páramo (2022); Saha et al. (2016); Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle (2011) to the conclusion that organizational learning can help

organizations achieve goals and raise the bar for performance and functioning. The research's conceptual framework is shown below.

Figure 1: A structural model examining the effect of PMS on managerial performance

2.1 Performance measurement system and managerial performance

Performance measurement systems are often used to explain favorable changes in organizational culture, systems, and procedures by businesses that concentrate on achieving a strategic vision (Neely et al. 2005); and (Memon and Ghani 2023).

The performance measurement system also provides information for management to understand the condition of the organization through financial and non-financial measures (Mio et al. 2022). Therefore, it is very important to see how the relationship between different managerial performance and performance measurement systems.

According to a study by Yuliansyah and Khan (2015), organizations can effectively motivate employees to use their competencies in completing assigned tasks by implementing a thorough performance measurement system. This can have a positive impact on overall performance. Due to the clarity of roles and their relation to company goals and strategies, the implications of implementing an effective performance measurement system also have a favorable impact on employees' cognitive abilities and inspire them to work harder.

According to Artz et al. (2012), utilizing a performance measuring system that encourages the influence of functional strategic decisions on performance has a favorable and substantial effect for a high level of performance specificity.

The empirical findings support the theory and provide evidence for the relationship between strategic performance measuring systems and managers' effectiveness. Thus, the following is the study's proposed hypothesis:

H1: *The performance measurement system has a positive effect on managerial performance.*

2.2 Performance measurement system and organizational learning

Communication and information theory provides a basis for predicting that performance measurement systems can assist in developing alignment of organizational goals (Chenhall 2005). The higher the expectations and pressures of the organizational environment in providing service quality, the more encouraging the development of learning organizations. Understanding the function of a performance assessment system requires an understanding of the dynamics of a comprehensive strategic management system. The essential tenet of organizational learning, according to De Lima et al. (2009), is the dialectic of the tasks carried out by a performance measuring system, which acts as a facilitator for either operational strategy implementation or management system change.

Rompho and Siengthai (2012) empirical findings revealed a beneficial relationship between organizational learning, performance measurement systems, and work-related abilities. According to Saha et al. (2016), organizational performance growth is achieved through the adoption of positive attitudes by individuals, groups, and organizations. These attitudes primarily enhance individual competence and organizational (management) competence through organizational learning. Strategic performance assessment systems and organizational learning have a positive link in the service setting, claim Yuliansyah and Jermias (2018). According to Edvardsson et al. (2005), the service industry depends heavily on labor. This description serves as the foundation for the following study's hypothesis:

H2: *Performance measurement systems have a positive effect on organizational learning.*

2.3 Organizational learning and managerial performance

An organization's learning objective is to offer a better means of achieving its overall goals at the individual, team, departmental, and organizational levels (Yuliansyah and Jermias 2018). Unsatisfactory outcomes from an employee can give the leadership a chance to assist their subordinates in improving performance. Feedback systems lead to learning. Learning is one of the strategies suggested by the leadership when the company notices disgruntled employees and wants to boost their performance.

The building of an environment that fosters innovation and long-term growth for businesses is one of the fundamental components of organizational learning (Escandon-Barbosa and Salas-Páramo 2022). Senge (1991) asserted that learning organizations should either produce existing results or foster the creation of new ones service. Additionally, Goh (2003) stress that learning organizations focus on embracing practices, frameworks, and policies that support learning. Furthermore, organizational learning, knowledge creation, acquisition, transfer, and integration lead to improved performance (Antunes and Pinheiro 2020); and (Jerez-Gomez et al. 2005).

Thus, organizational learning encourages the development of several innovations that directly and beneficially influence the development of managers' performance. This description forms the basis for the following research hypotheses:

H3: *Organizational learning has a positive effect on managerial performance.*

3. METHODOLOGY/RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Design and sample

This study used quantitative research design with cross section method. This research was conducted at the local government in Lampung province, Indonesia. Purposive sampling was used to take the samples. The requirements for the research sample were: first, the head of the Regional Work Unit (SKPD) and one level below. It is a unit that utilizes local government budgets and resources. Second, structural officials with a minimum working period of one year. The researcher distributed a questionnaire survey to 320 SKPD members in Lampung Provincial Government. A total of 149 participants responded to the survey, however, only 144 responses were considered for analysis in this study as five questionnaires were excluded owing to incompleteness.

AMOS software version 22.0 was used as an analysis approach of structural equation modeling (SEM). (Collier 2020) explains SEM namely: (1) allows researchers to analyze the effect of predictor variables on many dependent variables simultaneously; (2) allows researchers to account for measurement error and even overcome errors in predicting relationships; and (3) being able to test the entire model, not just focusing on individual relationships. To examine the model's appropriateness and causality assumptions, the estimated structural equation model was examined along with the whole model. Suitability models were assessed using the suggested goodness-of-fit model's criteria.

The final stage of structural equation model estimation is a full model analysis to see the suitability of the causality relationship built into the model. The relationship of model causality can be known based on the value of regression weight. If the critical ratio (CR) $> \pm 1.96$ with significance level < 0.05 then exogenous variables affect the endogenous variables, and if the value of CR $< \pm 1.96$ with significance level > 0.05 then exogenous variables have no effect on endogenous variables (Firmansyah et al. 2022).

3.2 Measurement instrument

Performance measurement system

A performance measurement system, as defined by Silvi et al. (2015), is a performance measurement system that combines finance, strategic business indicators, and operations to assess how well a company meets its target needs. Systems for measuring performance assist firms in focusing on long-term performance objectives and facilitate internal corporate strategy communication (Chenhall 2005).

The strategic performance measurement system in this study was measured using an instrument developed by Grafton et al. (2010) consisting of feed forward control and feedback control. The feed forward control consists of four questionnaires, namely: (1) setting performance goals; (2) guide the implementation of strategies; (3) develop an activity plan; (4) communicate the activity plan.

Feedback control consists of four questionnaires, namely: (1) promoting organizational learning; (2) analyze the impact of past decisions; (3) evaluating targets that have been achieved; and (4) identify the need for corrective action. Respondents were asked to rate how important each performance measurement system indicator was used in government organizations. The entire study variables were measured using a questionnaire with a Likert scale of 1 is “strongly disagree” and 5 is “strongly agree”. The higher the answer, the higher the variable degrees.

Organizational learning

According to the definitions of organizational learning offered by de Weerd-Nederhof et al. (2002); Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle (2011), organizational learning is the process by which businesses gain new knowledge and insights from the shared experiences of their employees. This process has the power to change behavior and strengthen a company's capabilities.

A four-item questionnaire created by Naman dan Slevin (1993) is used to measure organizational learning in a number of research, including Hult et al. (2000); Ketchen, Jr (2001); Henri (2006); dan Yuliansyah et al. (2019). These tools include: (1) employee learning is an investment rather than an expense; (2) learning is a fundamental value and a key to improvement; (3) once we stop learning, we imperil our future; and (4) the ability to learn is the major improvement. A 5-point Likert scale, where 1 means strongly disagree and 5 indicates strongly agree, was employed to measure the study's variables.

Managerial performance

Atiase et al. (2022) defines that managerial performance shows the personal effectiveness of managers, which is achieved by applying the right set of managerial competencies in the form of knowledge, skills, behaviors and attitudes that can contribute to organizational performance. Furthermore, performance is the quality of performance and productivity that has been achieved by employees in the work.

Four questions are used to assess the performance and productivity of managers in carrying out their duties. Questionnaires with a Likert scale of 1 for "strongly disagree" and 5 for "strongly agree" were used to collect data on all research variables. The variable degree increases with higher answer levels. Managerial performance variables were tested, and the results showed strong internal consistency, which was indicated by Cronbach's alpha of 0.61. Verify the accuracy of the results, which is validated by the fact that all data points show a significant correlation.

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Assessing reliability and validity

The first stage was to assess the reliability and validity of each indicator of the performance measurement system, managerial performance, and organizational learning. According to the findings shown in Table 1, it is evident that all variable indicators exhibit a significance value

of 0.001, denoted by a sign (p=***), so indicating their ability to elucidate the construct under investigation.

In addition, Amin et al. (2021) emphasized that the fit model of a construct tested by AMOS must meet convergent validity values, namely indicators with a loading factor above 0.50. Table 2 below displays convergent validity values for each indicator:

Table 1: Regression weights (reliability and validity test)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
PMS8	<---	PMS	1,000			
PMS7	<---	PMS	1,079	,127	8,495	***
PMS6	<---	PMS	,899	,137	6,558	***
PMS5	<---	PMS	,859	,156	5,502	***
PMS4	<---	PMS	,827	,153	5,391	***
PMS3	<---	PMS	,654	,135	4,852	***
PMS2	<---	PMS	,808	,164	4,924	***
PMS1	<---	PMS	,734	,166	4,428	***
MP1	<---	MP	1,000			
MP2	<---	MP	,917	,200	4,595	***
MP3	<---	MP	1,434	,286	5,012	***
MP4	<---	MP	1,030	,203	5,070	***
OL1	<---	OL	1,000			
OL2	<---	OL	1,146	,241	4,749	***
OL3	<---	OL	1,043	,218	4,777	***
OL4	<---	OL	1,117	,213	5,250	***

Table 2: Convergent validity

			Estimate
PMS8	<---	PMS	,714
PMS7	<---	PMS	,749
PMS6	<---	PMS	,627
PMS5	<---	PMS	,618
PMS4	<---	PMS	,548
PMS3	<---	PMS	,499
PMS2	<---	PMS	,513
PMS1	<---	PMS	,498
MP1	<---	MP	,500
MP2	<---	MP	,594
MP3	<---	MP	,704
MP4	<---	MP	,683
OL1	<---	OL	,606
OL2	<---	OL	,551
OL3	<---	OL	,551
OL4	<---	OL	,552

4.2 Assessment of structural model

The sample number required for this modeling is 100-200 (Lin et al. 2020). This sample size must be achieved using the maximum likelihood estimation technique. In order to meet the minimal sample size requirements, a sample size of 144 was gathered for this investigation. By examining the crucial skewness value of each indicator, the normality assumption test demonstrates that the data is univariately regularly distributed. The next stage after testing the SEM assumptions was assessing the goodness of fit indices full structural model criteria. Summary comparison of models constructed with the recommended cut-of goodness-of-fit indices. The results of testing the fit structural equation model produce a Chi-Square value of 1228.314 with a probability of $p = 0.000$, $TLI = 0.717$ and $CFI = 0.762$. The recommended values are $p > 0.05$, $TLI \geq 0.95$ and $CFI \geq 0.95$. The SEM fit value is below the recommendation indicating that the model is accepted at a marginal level. Meanwhile, the AIC and ECVI criteria show that the default model index is lower than the independence model, so the model is fit. Although some criteria can be accepted marginally, it is known that the Chi-square value is very sensitive to sample size, so there is a tendency for the Chi-square value to always be significant. Because of that it is suggested to ignore it and look for goodness that is more appropriate, if there are one or two criteria of goodness of fit then the model is good.

4.3 Tests of hypotheses

This analysis was carried out by considering the confirmatory factor analysis method for each construct. As a result, the procedure tests the model as a whole by using a model for each construct, resulting in a good model. Figure 2 shows the analysis of the structural equation model in full regarding the performance measurement system on managerial performance through organizational learning.

Figure 2: Full structural equation model

The output research hypothesis testing used AMOS program in the form of regression weights shown in Table 3 and Table 4. This table contains the critical ratio (CR), significance value or p-value, and parameter estimation. This table contains the critical ratio (CR), significance value or p-value, and estimate.

Table 3: Regression weights (hypothesis testing)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
OL	<---	PMS	,423	,100	4,242	***
MP	<---	PMS	-,220	,122	-1,798	,072
MP	<---	OL	1,042	,263	3,969	***

Table 4: Standardized regression weights

			Estimate
OL	<---	PMS	,605
MP	<---	PMS	-,317
MP	<---	OL	1,049

The first hypothesis (H1) states that the performance measurement system (PMS) has a positive effect on managerial performance (MP). The results of the estimation parameter test (standard regression weight) between performance measurement systems on managerial performance show an effect of -0.317. The critical ratio (CR) is -1.798 with a p-value at a significance level of 0.072. However, because the CR value < 1.96 and significance > 0.05 indicates that the performance measurement system has no significant effect on managerial performance. Thus hypothesis 1 is rejected. The findings of this study cannot support some of the results of previous studies, such as Baird (2017); Baird et al. (2021); and Aljuhmani et al. (2022) which found that the performance measurement system has a significant effect on organizational performance. Likewise with Davis and Albright (2004); Spencer et al. (2009) who previously stated that organizations that use performance measures are superior to organizations that do not use performance measures. This study provides strong empirical evidence to support Ittner et al. (2003); Lau and Sholihin (2005); and Sholihin et al. (2010), in his study concluded that the performance measurement system is not significantly related to manager performance. However, the influence of the performance measurement system is more on job satisfaction and depends on other contingent variables. Some possible contingent variables are: goal specificity, goal difficulty, organizational learning, and others.

The second hypothesis (H2) states that the performance measurement system (PMS) has a positive effect on organizational learning (OL). The test results on the estimation parameter (standardized regression weight) between performance measurement systems on organizational learning show an effect of 0.605. The critical ratio (CR) value is 4.242 with a p-value below a significance of 0.05 indicating that the performance measurement system has a positive effect on organizational learning. Thus hypothesis 2 is accepted. Related to the findings of this study, De Lima et al. (2009) explained the basic principle of organizational learning is the dialectic of the functions performed by a performance measurement system, which serves as a medium for implementing operational strategies or as a facilitator for redesigning

management systems. A study by Yuliansyah and Khan (2015) found that the implementation of a performance measurement system allows organizations to motivate employees to utilize their abilities and competencies in carrying out assigned tasks, employees will seek new understanding and experience that can improve their performance. Furthermore, Yuliansyah and Jermias (2018) explain that strategic performance measurement systems and organizational learning have a beneficial relationship.

The third hypothesis (H3) states that organizational learning (OL) has a positive effect on managerial performance (MP). The test results for the parameter estimation (standardized regression weight) between organizational learning and managerial performance show an effect of 1.049. The critical ratio (CR) value is 3.969 with a p-value below a significance of 0.05 indicating that organizational learning has a positive effect on managerial performance. Thus hypothesis 3 is accepted. The results of this study support the statement of Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle (2011) that organizational learning is an important factor for improving performance, where companies have the potential to change behavior and improve their capabilities by gaining new knowledge and insights from experience with employees. Organizational learning, according to Rebelo and Duarte Gomes (2011) is a technique that enables an organization to create, maintain, and modify organizational memory by giving instructions for organizational behavior.

This study of organizational learning in local government organizations provides support for previous research, such as Antunes and Pinheiro (2020); dan Jerez-Gomez et al. (2005) organizational learning, knowledge creation, acquisition, transfer, and integration lead to increased performance. Organizational learning on managerial performance in this study has the strongest degree of influence compared to the influence of other variable paths. In addition, the effect of the performance measurement system on managerial performance is not directly significant and even tends to be negative. Thus, organizational learning has a very important role in linking performance measurement systems to managerial performance, especially in government organizations. Saha et al. (2016) provide support that the achievement of organizational performance development lies in the positive attitudes of individuals, groups, and organizations which primarily improve individual competence as well as organizational management competence through organizational learning. To provide an understanding of the direct and indirect effects of the performance measurement system, it can be seen in Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5: Standardized direct effects

	PMS	OL	MP
OL	,605	,000	,000
MP	-,317	1,049	,000

Table 6: Standardized Indirect Effects

	PMS	OL	MP
OL	,000	,000	,000
MP	,634	,000	,000

Table 5 shows the direct effect of performance measurement systems on managerial performance and organizational learning, as well as organizational learning on managerial performance. Based on the table, this study found that the effect of the performance measurement system on managerial performance was very weak, even negative. This shows that the performance measurement system in local government organizations cannot improve managerial performance like some previous studies. However, in contrast to performance measurement systems on organizational learning, the effect is significant.

Table 6 shows the indirect effect of the performance measurement system on managerial performance. The results of the study found that the role of organizational learning was very large, namely 0.634 (compared to a direct effect of 0.317). Thus it can be said that organizational learning is a factor that needs to be considered in mediating the influence of performance measurement systems on managerial performance.

5. CONCLUSION

Contingency theory emerged as an answer to the universalistic approach and argues that optimal control designs can be applied to the firm as a whole. The contingency approach is based on the view that organizational effectiveness results from appropriate administrative practices, such as performance measurement systems to the contingent factors in which the organization operates. The research results prove this, where the relationship between organizational characteristics such as performance measurement systems and managerial performance depends on contingencies or certain factors.

The main finding of this study is that organizational learning mediates the relationship between performance measurement systems and managerial performance in government organizations. The significant indirect effect of performance measurement systems on managerial performance through organizational learning is consistent with the results reported by Chenhall (2005). Research also provides support to Yuliansyah and Khan (2015); Yuliansyah and Jermias (2018) that the implementation of a performance measurement system allows organizations to motivate employees to seek new understanding and experiences that can improve their performance. However, it was explained that the performance measurement system has no direct effect on manager performance to Ittner et al. (2003); Lau and Sholihin (2005); and Sholihin et al. (2010). The results are not significant for performance measurement systems with managerial performance as there are several plausible reasons for these inconsistent results. First, the research results show that government sector organizations have performance measurement systems that tend to be standardized and static so that most structural employees, especially at the managerial level, are not internally motivated. Second, our findings show that one of the characteristics of government organizations is to focus on public services without expecting financial benefits and to make policies and decisions based on consensus. In this situation, government organizations tend to use performance measures as a basis for conducting learning within the organization, not directly influencing attitudes and behavior in improving performance.

The novelty of this study is that organizational learning is used as a mediating variable to test whether the performance measurement system affects the performance of managers. The research results offer new understanding, especially in local government organizations, about how the various variables above interact in one model. The results of this study did not find the effect of the performance measurement system on managerial performance, even the relationship between the two variables tends to be negative. However, research has found new empirical evidence, especially in local government organizations, that performance measurement systems have a significant influence on organizational learning. Furthermore, organizational learning and managerial performance have the strongest significant effect among the other variables. The results of this study explicitly conclude that the influence of performance measurement systems on managerial performance tends to be indirect, but rather depends on the role of organizational learning. Finally, the studies according to contingency theory, the complexity of management behavior and management control practices including performance measurement systems are key factors in organizational control as explained by Chenhall (2003); and Cheng and Fisk (2022). This study also finds that strategic performance measurement systems affect organizational learning and thus influence performance.

This study is subject to several limitations that should be considered when drawing conclusions from the results. *First*, the present study employed a restricted sample of local government organisations situated in Lampung Province, Indonesia. Consequently, there exists a potential limitation in terms of generalizability of the research findings. Therefore, future research is expected to explore the use of a wider sample and involve various existing local government organizations. *Second*, the study does not consider the influence of other contextual variables. Extensions to this study could investigate the extent to which contextual variables influence the predicted relationships. Future research could investigate the influence of different culture in organization and information technology capabilities, as predicted these can create controlling system that may influence managerial performance.

Notwithstanding the limitations of the study, the results suggest that much can be learned about the role of performance measurement systems in promoting effective performance in government organizations. In addition, this study provides an overview about how the Amos application can be used to explore performance measurement systems to help improve managerial performance, with organizational learning chosen as the intervening variable.

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References

- 1) Ahmad, K., Zabri, S. M., and Atan, S. A. (2022). "Multidimensional performance measures and factors and their linkage with performance." *International Journal of Emerging Markets*.
- 2) Akgün, A. E., Keskin, H., Aksoy, Z., Samil Fidan, S., and Yigital, S. (2023). "The mediating role of organizational learning capability and resilience in the error management culture-service innovation link and the contingent effect of error frequency." *The Service Industries Journal*, 43(7-8), 525-554.

- 3) Aljuhmani, H. Y., Ababneh, B., Emeagwali, L., and Elrehail, H. (2022). "Strategic stances and organizational performance: Are strategic performance measurement systems the missing link?" *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*(ahead-of-print).
- 4) Amin, M., Shamim, A., Ghazali, Z., and Khan, I. (2021). "Employee motivation to co-create value (EMCCV): construction and validation of scale." *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 58, 102334.
- 5) Antunes, H. d. J. G., and Pinheiro, P. G. (2020). "Linking knowledge management, organizational learning and memory." *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 5(2), 140-149.
- 6) Appuhami, R. (2019). "Exploring the relationship between strategic performance measurement systems and managers' creativity: the mediating role of psychological empowerment and organisational learning." *Accounting & Finance*, 59(4), 2201-2233.
- 7) Artz, M., Homburg, C., and Rajab, T. (2012). "Performance-measurement system design and functional strategic decision influence: The role of performance-measure properties." *Accounting, organizations and society*, 37(7), 445-460.
- 8) Atiase, V. Y., Sarpong, D., Agbanyo, S., and Ameh, J. K. (2022). "Crafting Organisational Resilience Through Managerial Performance", *The African Context of Business and Society*. Emerald Publishing Limited, pp. 77-94.
- 9) Baird, K. (2017). "The effectiveness of strategic performance measurement systems." *International journal of productivity and performance management*, 66(1), 3-21.
- 10) Baird, K., Su, S. X., and Nuhu, N. (2021). "The mediating role of fairness on the effectiveness of strategic performance measurement systems." *Personnel Review*, 51(5), 1491-1517.
- 11) Bellora-Bienengrüber, L., Radtke, R. R., and Widener, S. K. (2022). "Counterproductive work behaviors and work climate: The role of an ethically focused management control system and peers' self-focused behavior." *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 96, 101275.
- 12) Beuren, I. M., dos Santos, V., and Bernd, D. C. (2021). "Effects of using the management control system on individual performance with the intervenience of feedforward and organizational learning." *Journal of Knowledge Management*.
- 13) Cadez, S., and Guilding, C. (2008). "An exploratory investigation of an integrated contingency model of strategic management accounting." *Accounting, organizations and society*, 33(7-8), 836-863.
- 14) Chakravarty, A., Grewal, R., and Sambamurthy, V. (2013). "Information technology competencies, organizational agility, and firm performance: Enabling and facilitating roles." *Information systems research*, 24(4), 976-997.
- 15) Cheng, Y., and Fisk, A. (2022). "Contingency theory informs relationship management: Exploring the contingent organization-public relationships (COPR) in a crisis of Mainland China." *Public Relations Review*, 48(2), 102178.
- 16) Chenhall, R. H. (2003). "Management control systems design within its organizational context: findings from contingency-based research and directions for the future." *Accounting, organizations and society*, 28(2-3), 127-168.
- 17) Chenhall, R. H. (2005). "Integrative strategic performance measurement systems, strategic alignment of manufacturing, learning and strategic outcomes: an exploratory study." *Accounting, organizations and society*, 30(5), 395-422.
- 18) Chenhall, R. H., Kallunki, J.-P., and Silvola, H. (2011). "Exploring the relationships between strategy, innovation, and management control systems: The roles of social networking, organic innovative culture, and formal controls." *Journal of management accounting research*, 23(1), 99-128.

- 19) Collier, J. (2020). *Applied structural equation modeling using AMOS: Basic to advanced techniques*: Routledge.
- 20) Davis, S., and Albright, T. (2004). "An investigation of the effect of balanced scorecard implementation on financial performance." *Management accounting research*, 15(2), 135-153.
- 21) De Lima, E. P., da Costa, S. E. G., and Angelis, J. J. (2009). "Strategic performance measurement systems: a discussion about their roles." *Measuring Business Excellence*.
- 22) de Weerd-Nederhof, P. C., Pacitti, B. J., da Silva Gomes, J. F., and Pearson, A. W. (2002). "Tools for the improvement of organizational learning processes in innovation." *Journal of workplace learning*.
- 23) Do, H., Budhwar, P., Shipton, H., Nguyen, H.-D., and Nguyen, B. (2022). "Building organizational resilience, innovation through resource-based management initiatives, organizational learning and environmental dynamism." *Journal of Business Research*, 141, 808-821.
- 24) Eddine Bedoui, M. H. (2012). "Shari 'a-based ethical performance measurement framework."
- 25) Edvardsson, B., Gustafsson, A., and Roos, I. (2005). "Service portraits in service research: a critical review." *International journal of service industry management*.
- 26) Escandon-Barbosa, D., and Salas-Páramo, J. (2022). "The role of informal institutions in the relationship between innovation and organisational learning in export performance: A bidirectional relation?" *Asia Pacific Management Review*.
- 27) Firmansyah, I. A., Yasirandi, R., and Utomo, R. G. (2022). "The influence of efficacy, credibility, and normative pressure to M-banking adoption level in Indonesia." *Procedia Computer Science*, 197, 51-60.
- 28) Grafton, J., Lillis, A. M., and Widener, S. K. (2010). "The role of performance measurement and evaluation in building organizational capabilities and performance." *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 35(7), 689-706.
- 29) Hall, M. (2011). "Do comprehensive performance measurement systems help or hinder managers' mental model development?" *Management accounting research*, 22(2), 68-83.
- 30) Henri, J.-F. (2006). "Management control systems and strategy: A resource-based perspective." *Accounting, organizations and society*, 31(6), 529-558.
- 31) Ittner, C. D., Larcker, D. F., and Randall, T. (2003). "Performance implications of strategic performance measurement in financial services firms." *Accounting, organizations and society*, 28(7-8), 715-741.
- 32) Jerez-Gomez, P., Céspedes-Lorente, J., and Valle-Cabrera, R. (2005). "Organizational learning capability: a proposal of measurement." *Journal of business research*, 58(6), 715-725.
- 33) Jiménez-Jiménez, D., and Sanz-Valle, R. (2011). "Innovation, organizational learning, and performance." *Journal of business research*, 64(4), 408-417.
- 34) Kihn, L. A. (2010). "Performance outcomes in empirical management accounting research: Recent developments and implications for future research." *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*.
- 35) Kim, T. H., Lee, J.-N., Chun, J. U., and Benbasat, I. (2014). "Understanding the effect of knowledge management strategies on knowledge management performance: A contingency perspective." *Information & management*, 51(4), 398-416.
- 36) Lau, C. M., and Sholihin, M. (2005). "Financial and nonfinancial performance measures: How do they affect job satisfaction?" *The British Accounting Review*, 37(4), 389-413.

- 37) Lin, H. M., Lee, M. H., Liang, J. C., Chang, H. Y., Huang, P., and Tsai, C. C. (2020). "A review of using partial least square structural equation modeling in e-learning research." *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 51(4), 1354-1372.
- 38) Louhichi, A., and Boujelbene, Y. (2016). "Credit risk, managerial behaviour and macroeconomic equilibrium within dual banking systems: Interest-free vs. interest-based banking industries." *Research in International Business and Finance*, 38, 104-121.
- 39) Mahama, H. (2006). "Management control systems, cooperation and performance in strategic supply relationships: A survey in the mines." *Management Accounting Research*, 17(3), 315-339.
- 40) Memon, K. R., and Ghani, B. (2023). "The relationship between performance appraisal system and employees' voice behavior through the mediation-moderation mechanism." *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 12(2), 220-241.
- 41) Mio, C., Costantini, A., and Panfilo, S. (2022). "Performance measurement tools for sustainable business: A systematic literature review on the sustainability balanced scorecard use." *Corporate social responsibility and environmental management*, 29(2), 367-384.
- 42) Neely, A., Gregory, M., and Platts, K. (2005). "Performance measurement system design: A literature review and research agenda." *International journal of operations & production management*, 25(12), 1228-1263.
- 43) Qalati, S. A., Zafar, Z., Fan, M., Limón, M. L. S., and Khaskheli, M. B. (2022). "Employee performance under transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior: A mediated model." *Heliyon*, 8(11), e11374.
- 44) Rebelo, T. M., and Duarte Gomes, A. (2011). "Conditioning factors of an organizational learning culture." *Journal of workplace learning*, 23(3), 173-194.
- 45) Rey-Marston, M., and Neely, A. (2010). "Beyond words: testing alignment among inter-organizational performance measures." *Measuring Business Excellence*.
- 46) Rompho, B., and Siengthai, S. (2012). "Integrated performance measurement system for firm's human capital building." *Journal of Intellectual Capital*.
- 47) Saadat, V., and Saadat, Z. (2016). "Organizational learning as a key role of organizational success." *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 230, 219-225.
- 48) Saha, N., Chatterjee, B., Gregar, A., and Saha, P. (2016). "The impact of SHRM on sustainable organizational learning and performance development." *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 5, 63-75.
- 49) Serna, L. R., Bowyer, D. M., and Gregory, S. K. (2022). "Management control systems. A non-family stakeholder perspective on the critical success factors influencing continuous stakeholder support during businesses succession." *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*(ahead-of-print).
- 50) Sholihin, M., Pike, R., and Mangena, M. (2010). "Reliance on multiple performance measures and manager performance." *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*.
- 51) Silvi, R., Bartolini, M., Raffoni, A., and Visani, F. (2015). "The practice of strategic performance measurement systems: Models, drivers and information effectiveness." *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*.
- 52) Spencer, X., Joiner, T. A., and Salmon, S. (2009). "Differentiation Strategy, Performance Measurement Systems and Organizational Performance: Evidence from Australia." *International Journal of Business*, 14(1).

- 53) Tjahjadi, B., Soewarno, N., Astri, E., and Hariyati, H. (2019). "Does intellectual capital matter in performance management system-organizational performance relationship? Experience of higher education institutions in Indonesia." *Journal of intellectual capital*.
- 54) Umashev, C., and Willett, R. (2008). "Challenges to implementing strategic performance measurement systems in multi-objective organizations: the case of a large local government authority." *Abacus*, 44(4), 377-398.
- 55) Yuliansyah, Y., and Jermias, J. (2018). "Strategic performance measurement system, organizational learning and service strategic alignment: Impact on performance." *International Journal of Ethics and Systems*.
- 56) Yuliansyah, Y., and Khan, A. A. (2015). "Strategic performance measurement system: a service sector and lower level employees empirical investigation." *Corporate Ownership and Control*, 12(3), 304-316.
- 57) Yuliansyah, Y., Khan, A. A., and Fadhilah, A. (2019). "Strategic performance measurement system, firm capabilities and customer-focused strategy." *Pacific Accounting Review*.